

Environmental context matters for interpreting species differences in *Pan* aggression

(Comment on Bryon et al (2026), Chimpanzees are not more aggressive than bonobos but target sexes differently, *Science Advances*)

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Abstract

This commentary addresses the findings of Bryon et al. (2026, *Science Advances*), who use multi-zoo data on bonobos and chimpanzees to infer species-typical patterns of aggression under standardized conditions. We argue this inference is problematic for two reasons. First, ecological and social variation in the wild is not noise but relevant context, so flattening food, ranging, intergroup competition, and mating contexts can obscure evolved differences. Second, captivity introduces strong, species-atypical confounds such as constrained ranging, altered group composition, and active management of aggression, which can systematically affect behavior. We therefore caution against treating zoo-based comparisons as decisive evidence for evolved species differences and advocate integrating captive with ecologically relevant wild data.

Introduction

Understanding the evolutionary and proximate mechanisms that shape aggressive behavior is a central topic in behavioral ecology, and clarifying species- and sex-based differences in aggression in the genus *Pan* is highly informative for reconstructing the evolution of aggression in hominins (Hare et al., 2012; Wrangham, 2018). A recent example is an empirical article by Bryon et al. (2026), who use an impressive multigroup dataset from 22 zoo-housed bonobo and chimpanzee groups to compare patterns of species- and sex-specific aggression. The authors argue that controlling ecological variables in captivity allows potential differences in aggression to be “more confidently attributed to hardwired adaptive species-level effects...rather than a consequence of direct environmental pressures.” While we regard the Bryon et al. (2026) study as a valuable contribution to understanding patterns of aggression in zoo housed bonobos and chimpanzees, we identify two fundamental issues with its conceptual framework: first, ecological variation in the wild is portrayed as noise rather than as an integral part of the phenotype, and second, zoo settings are broadly assumed to remove, rather than introduce, relevant confounds. We will explain these issues in more detail in the following paragraphs.

1) Environmental variation is relevant context, not noise.

In evolutionary biology, traits are expressed in particular environments, and gene–environment interactions are central to evolutionary processes (Pigliucci, 2001; West-Eberhard, 2003). For example, the ways in which aggression is shaped by ecological and social environments at individual, population, and species levels constitute a meaningful reaction norm across different environmental conditions (Via & Lande, 1985). While the authors recognize that “aggression serves as a strategic tool for securing vital resources such as territory, food and mates”, their framing of ecological variables as mere “confounds” to be controlled for underemphasizes the extent to which those variables themselves constitute meaningful components of species-typical behavioral expression. By aiming to flatten ecological variation and associated social dynamics in a zoo setting (e.g., variation in food availability, subgroup size and membership, mate competition, and pressure from neighboring groups), researchers risk altering the conditions under which species differences emerge and are biologically meaningful, as well as the contexts in which decisions to escalate conflict into aggression occur (Wittig & Boesch, 2003).

If bonobos and chimpanzees evolved different aggression strategies in response to, for example, variation in food distribution (Furuichi, 2009), ranging patterns (Furuichi, 2009), female reproductive signaling (Douglas et al., 2016; Ryu et al., 2025), and mate competition (Muller & Wrangham, 2004; Surbeck et al., 2012), then placing both species into highly regulated environments with consistently available food, no predation risk, and managed reproduction could attenuate, reshape, or in some cases alter the apparent expression of evolved differences. Importantly, given that intergroup competition is a key context underlying our current understanding of species differences in the expression of aggression (Mouginot et al., 2024; Shibata & Furuichi, 2024; Wilson et al., 2014), the absence of competing neighboring groups also removes one of the arguably most relevant contexts for variation in male aggression and alters within-group dynamics in unpredictable ways (Lemoine et al., 2020). Consequently, the presence or absence of species differences in aggression within zoo settings does not provide reliable evidence for “hardwired” species-typical traits.

2) Zoo settings do not simply remove confounds; they create new ones.

The constrained ranging within enclosures, enforced proximity, food provisioning, artificial group sizes and composition, the lack of fission–fusion dynamics and altered mate competition dynamics through birth control in most zoos (Wallace et al., 2016), all constitute strong, unnatural environmental alterations for *Pan* species. These factors considerably influence the expression of aggression (Videan & Fritz, 2007; Williams et al., 2010) and can systematically affect it in ways that are difficult to capture or model in comparative analyses of zoo-housed populations, including that of Bryon et al.(2026). For example, it is difficult to interpret a mean contact aggression rate of 0.10 acts per observation hour per adult chimpanzee male in Bryon et al (2026; Fig 2), which is nearly 7 times higher than the reported 0.013 acts per observation hour per adult male chimpanzee reported from the Gombe population (Mouginot et al., 2024). Group composition including adult sex ratios (Hohmann & Fruth, 2003; Watts, 2022), kinship ties (Langergraber et al., 2007; Surbeck et al., 2011), the number of receptive females (Furuichi, 2011; Ryu et al., 2025; Sobolewski et al., 2013), and social bonds (Wittig & Boesch, 2003) have been shown, among other factors, to influence competitive dynamics within and between the sexes in *Pan*. For example, while bonobos live in the wild in mixed sex groups including 2-10 adult males (average around 5 adult males; Furuichi et al., 2023; McLester & Fruth, 2023; Samuni et al., 2022), the average number of adult males in bonobo groups in Bryon et al.(2026) is approximately 1.7, with five out of the 13 bonobo groups having only a single adult male present and two additional groups having no adult male present. Given that the expression of aggression reflects competitive dynamics that are inherently linked to socio-demographic factors, interspecific comparisons made under the artificial demographics of zoo settings may reflect management decisions more than evolved, species-typical behavioral patterns.

Furthermore, rearing histories, transfers between institutions, patterns of human-ape interaction, feeding and enrichment regimes, and psychopharmaceutical interventions are often designed explicitly to manage aggression (Bloomsmith et al., 1994; Caws et al., 2008; Richard et al., 2020). Each of these factors, which differ across zoos and may also differ systematically between *Pan* species, is therefore likely to have a direct impact on social behavior, especially aggression. Importantly, because these variables are difficult to standardize or retrospectively control, any conclusion that these settings effectively minimize most environmental confounds should be interpreted with caution. Therefore, it is important to recognize that Bryon et al., (2026) produces results under a very specific and species-atypical set of constraints. In this respect, although zoo comparisons can help illuminate the behavioral flexibility of a species under their particular conditions, their divergent ecological contexts preclude any definitive conclusions about hard-wired traits.

Conclusions and Outlook

When considered together with studies of wild populations, carefully controlled experiments in zoo settings can reveal important insights into behavioral and cognitive capacities and their underlying psychological mechanisms (Kalan & Tennie, 2026; McEwen et al., 2022). However, when behavior is sensitive to social and ecological conditions that are likely to differ between zoos and adaptive contexts in the wild, caution is needed when interpreting such results as evidence for species typical adaptations. We acknowledge that even field studies can struggle to meet the requirement

of a relevant adaptive context, given the anthropogenic pressure at many sites (Berger-Tal et al., 2025; Hockings et al., 2015) and as a community we should strive to help to alleviate these pressures. Our aim is therefore not to single out this particular study, but rather to underscore the conceptual challenges that must be considered whenever data from *Pan* living under unnatural conditions are used to draw conclusions about evolved, species-typical patterns of social behavior. We value the use of multi-population comparisons, and understanding whether species differences (or similarities) observed in zoos reflect evolved, species-level traits may benefit most from integrating evidence across captive and representative wild settings, as these approaches provide complementary insights into behavioral expression (Kalan & Tennie, 2026). Otherwise, there is a need for evidence that social and ecological conditions do not alter the context, structure, or function of the specific trait in question. Given the well-documented plasticity of primate behavior, including aggression (e.g. Sabbi et al., 2021), this is a demanding standard to meet.

Citations

- Berger-Tal, O., Saltz, D., Michelangeli, M., & Wong, B. B. M. (2025). Anthropogenic change and the loss of behavioural diversity. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 292(2060), 20252097.
- Bloomsmith, M. A., Laule, G. E., Alford, P. L., & Thurston, R. H. (1994). Using training to moderate chimpanzee aggression during feeding. *Zoo Biology*, 13(6), 557–566.
- Bryon, E., Roth, T. S., Torfs, J. R. R., Eens, M., van Leeuwen, E. J. C., & Staes, N. (2026). Chimpanzees are not more aggressive than bonobos but target sexes differently. *Science Advances*, 12(11), 1–11.
- Caws, C. E., Wehnelt, S., & Aureli, F. (2008). The effect of a new vertical structure in mitigating aggressive behaviour in a large group of chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*). *Animal Welfare*, 17(2), 149–154.
- Douglas, P. H., Hohmann, G., Murtagh, R., Thiessen-Bock, R., & Deschner, T. (2016). Mixed messages: Wild female bonobos show high variability in the timing of ovulation in relation to sexual swelling patterns. *BMC Evolutionary Biology*, 16, 1–17.
- Furuichi, T. (2009). Factors underlying party size differences between chimpanzees and bonobos: A review and hypotheses for future study. *Primates*, 50(3), 197–209.
- Furuichi, T. (2011). Female contributions to the peaceful nature of bonobo society. *Evolutionary Anthropology: Issues, News, and Reviews*, 20(4), 131–142.
- Furuichi, T., Ihobe, H., Kimura, D., & Hashimoto, C. (2023). *Bonobos and People at Wamba: 50 Years of Research*. Springer.
- Hare, B., Wobber, V., & Wrangham, R. (2012). The self-domestication hypothesis: Evolution of bonobo psychology is due to selection against aggression. *Animal Behaviour*, 83(3), 573–585.
- Hockings, K. J., McLennan, M. R., Carvalho, S., Ancrenaz, M., Bobe, R., Byrne, R. W., Dunbar, R. I. M., Matsuzawa, T., McGrew, W. C., Williamson, E. A., Wilson, M. L., Wood, B., Wrangham, R. W., & Hill, C. M. (2015). Apes in the Anthropocene: Flexibility and survival. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 30(4), 215–222.
- Hohmann, G., & Fruth, B. (2003). Intra- and inter-sexual aggression by bonobos in the context of mating. *Behaviour*, 140, 1389–1413.
- Kalan, A. K., & Tennie, C. (2026). Brokering peace in the ape (culture) wars. *Evolutionary Human Sciences*, 8, e9.
- Langergraber, K. E., Mitani, J. C., & Vigilant, L. (2007). The limited impact of kinship on cooperation in wild chimpanzees. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 104(19), 7786–7790.
- Lemoine, S., Preis, A., Samuni, L., Boesch, C., Crockford, C., & Wittig, R. M. (2020). Between-Group Competition Impacts Reproductive Success in Wild Chimpanzees. *Current Biology*, 30(2), 312–318.e3.
- McEwen, E. S., Warren, E., Tenpas, S., Jones, B., Durdevic, K., Rapport Munro, E., & Call, J. (2022). Primate cognition in zoos: Reviewing the impact of zoo-based research over 15 years. *American Journal of Primatology*, 84(10), e23369.
- McLester, E., & Fruth, B. (2023). Golden-bellied mangabeys (*Cercocebus chrysogaster*) exhibit a larger home range and longer travel distances than those of bonobos (*Pan paniscus*) at LuiKotale, Democratic Republic of the Congo. *American Journal of Primatology*, 85(6), e23486.
- Mouginot, M., Wilson, M. L., Desai, N., & Surbeck, M. (2024). Differences in expression of male aggression between wild bonobos and chimpanzees. *Current Biology*, 0(0), 1–11.
- Muller, M. N., & Wrangham, R. W. (2004). Dominance, aggression and testosterone in wild chimpanzees: A test of the “challenge hypothesis.” *Animal Behaviour*, 67, 113–123.
- Pigliucci, M. (2001). *Phenotypic plasticity: Beyond nature and nurture*. JHU Press.

- Richard, R., Boren, B., & Becker, J. (2020). The use of citalopram hydrobromide to manage aggression in a male chimpanzee (*Pan troglodytes*). *Journal of Zoo and Wildlife Medicine*, 50(4), 1005–1007.
- Ryu, H., Hashimoto, C., Hill, D. A., Mouri, K., Shimizu, K., & Furuichi, T. (2025). Male bonobo mating strategies target female fertile windows despite noisy ovulatory signals during sexual swelling. *PLOS Biology*, 23(12), e3003503.
- Sabbi, K. H., Emery Thompson, M., Machanda, Z. P., Otali, E., Wrangham, R. W., & Muller, M. N. (2021). Sex differences in early experience and the development of aggression in wild chimpanzees. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(12), e2017144118.
- Samuni, L., Langergraber, K. E., & Surbeck, M. H. (2022). Characterization of Pan social systems reveals in-group/out-group distinction and out-group tolerance in bonobos. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(26), e2201122119.
- Shibata, S., & Furuichi, T. (2024). Comparative analysis of intragroup intermale relationships: A study of wild bonobos (*Pan paniscus*) in Wamba, Democratic Republic of Congo and chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*) in Kalinzu Forest Reserve, Uganda. *Primates*, 65(4), 243–255.
- Sobolewski, M. E., Brown, J. L., & Mitani, J. C. (2013). Female parity, male aggression, and the Challenge Hypothesis in wild chimpanzees. *Primates*, 54(1), 81–88.
- Surbeck, M., Deschner, T., Schubert, G., Weltring, A., & Hohmann, G. (2012). Mate competition, testosterone and intersexual relationships in bonobos, *Pan paniscus*. *Animal Behaviour*, 83(3), 659–669.
- Surbeck, M., Mundry, R., & Hohmann, G. (2011). Mothers matter! Maternal support, dominance status and mating success in male bonobos (*Pan paniscus*). *Proceedings of the Royal Society B-Biological Sciences*, 278(1705), 590–598.
- Via, S., & Lande, R. (1985). Genotype-Environment Interaction and the Evolution of Phenotypic Plasticity. *Evolution*, 39(3), 505–522.
- Videan, E. N., & Fritz, J. (2007). Effects of short- and long-term changes in spatial density on the social behavior of captive chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*). *Applied Animal Behaviour Science*, 102(1), 95–105. h
- Wallace, P. Y., Asa, C. S., Agnew, M., & Cheyne, S. M. (2016). A review of population control methods in captive-housed primates. *Animal Welfare*, 25(1), 7–20.
- Watts, D. P. (2022). Male chimpanzee sexual coercion and mating success at Ngogo. *American Journal of Primatology*, 84(2), e23361. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.23361>
- West-Eberhard, M. J. (2003). *Developmental plasticity and evolution*. Oxford University Press.
- Williams, R. C., Nash, L. T., Scarry, C. J., Videan, E. N., & Fritz, J. (2010). Factors affecting wounding aggression in a colony of captive chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*). *Zoo Biology*, 29(3), 351–364.
- Wilson, M. L., Boesch, C., Fruth, B., Furuichi, T., Gilby, I. C., Hashimoto, C., Hobaiter, C. L., Hohmann, G., Itoh, N., Koops, K., Lloyd, J. N., Matsuzawa, T., Mitani, J. C., Mjungu, D. C., Morgan, D., Muller, M. N., Mundry, R., Nakamura, M., Pruett, J., ... Wrangham, R. W. (2014). Lethal aggression in *Pan* is better explained by adaptive strategies than human impacts. *Nature*, 513(7518), 414–417.
- Wittig, R. M., & Boesch, C. (2003). “Decision-making” in conflicts of wild chimpanzees (*Pan troglodytes*): An extension of the Relational Model. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, 54(5), 491–504.
- Wrangham, R. W. (2018). Two types of aggression in human evolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(2), 245–253.